

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D9.4 COMMON ACTION PLAN ON CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Common Action Plan on Clustering Activities is written in the framework of WP9 Project Management and Coordination (Task 9.4 Clustering and Interactions with Other Projects) of the IN-HABIT Project under Grant Agreement No. 869227. The aim of the Common Action Plan on Clustering Activities is to build on the established contacts with other project coordinators for further collaboration, especially with those projects funded under the “Smart and Sustainable Cities” call, as well as with sister projects funded under the same topic SC5-14-2019 “Visionary and integrated solutions to improve well-being and health in cities”.

After several meetings with sister projects ([VARCITIES](#), [GOGREENROUTES](#) and [euPOLIS](#)) a series of joint actions are delineated in this deliverable, based on the agreed cross-cutting issues and result sharing among the 4 projects, such as creating common baseline and indicators for wellbeing and health, address the gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion (GDE&I) perspective, as well as develop joint communication and dissemination activities.

The Common Action Plan on Clustering Activities is a living document, and regular updates of this deliverable will be promoted, when new joint activities are agreed with sister projects and other projects dealing with issues addressed by IN-HABIT. This information will be updated on the periodical meetings hosted with the representatives of the sister projects. IN-HABIT Steering Committee and General Assembly will be informed on the decisions taken and the participation of the partners involved requested. Each time the document is updated all partners will be duly informed about it.

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ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AINOW	Artificial Intelligence NOW Institute
BOT	Book On a Tree LTD
D	Deliverable
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach
DEI	Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion
EASME	Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
EU	European Union
GDE&I	Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion
GPS	Global Positioning System
IHW	Inclusive Health and Wellbeing
ISIM	isIMPACT
M	Month
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
PA	Project Advisor
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RISE IMET	International Conference on Emerging Technologies and the Digital Transformation of Museums and Heritage Sites
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SMSCs	Small and Medium Size Cities
TSR	Tesseract Urban Social Research – Colini-Tripodi GBR
UCO	University of Cordoba
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UREAD	University of Reading
VIS	Visionary and Integrated Solutions
WP	Work Package
WPLs	Work Package Leaders
WTG	Wellness TechGroup - Wellness Telecom

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1. INTRODUCTION

The IN-HABIT Project (INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies) aims to test visionary and integrated solutions (VIS) to foster Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW) in four peripheral small and medium size cities (SMSCs) - Cordoba (Spain), Riga (Latvia), Lucca (Italy) and Nitra (Slovakia) – with a focus on gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion. Bogota city in Colombia will contribute sharing knowledge and replicating actions.

IN-HABIT visionary approach consists of the innovative mobilisation of existing undervalued resources (culture, food, human-animal bonds and art and environment) to increase IHW. The integrated approach is based on a combination of technological, digital, nature-based, cultural, and social innovations in selected urban public spaces. These solutions will be co-designed, co-deployed and co-managed with and by local stakeholders and residents.

Deliverable 9.4 deals with the clustering activities that the project will develop with sister projects (VARCITIES, GOGREEN ROUTES, euPOLIS) and other relevant projects addressing related topics to IN-HABIT. It will integrate such information by reporting on the principal areas of cooperation and the joint actions to be undertaken with these projects in terms of clustering activities. The deliverable aims to delineate future cross-project cooperation, consultation and joint activities on cross-cutting issues and share of working methods and results, as well as joint communication and dissemination activities.

The structure of the document follows the activities that have already been agreed with sister projects and under the coordination of the Project Advisors of such projects after the two coordination meetings celebrated in November 2020 and January 2021.

The document is organised as follows: Chapter 1 includes a short Introduction; Chapter 2 states the actions agreed, the actions developed and the actions suggested by the IN-HABIT project, in terms of baseline evaluation and indicators for wellbeing and health; Chapter 3 states the actions agreed, the actions developed and the actions suggested by the IN-HABIT project in terms of gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion; Chapter 4 states the actions agreed, the actions developed and the actions suggested by the IN-HABIT project in terms of joint communication and dissemination activities.

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2. WELLBEING AND HEALTH AT THE LOCAL LEVEL

The main outputs of this area of cooperation would be:

- To draft a joint Manifesto on Health and Wellbeing based on the subsidiarity principle
- To agree on a list of common indicators associated to the diverse types of solutions
- To align the join proposal of indicators to those included in the NBS Handbook on Indicators and Assessment that is currently being developed, with the aim to broaden the spectrum of solutions analysed.
- To elaborate a join deliverable gathering all this information.

2.1 Actions agreed in the Second Online Clustering Meeting

After the 2nd Online Clustering Meeting celebrated on 27th February, the representative partners of the sister projects agreed to develop the following actions:

- **A Manifesto with a common narrative on the subsidiarity principle applied to wellbeing and health.** The Manifesto will include the following aspects or questions to be addressed:

How can we define health and wellbeing at the local level? What is “locality” in this respect? Are we considering the whole city, just a district, or a neighbourhood? Could we use GPS coordinates? This Manifesto could complement the work that the [OECD is doing on wellbeing at regional level](#) (Better Life Initiative: Measuring Well-Being and Progress).

- **A joint deliverable based on a list of common indicators** (defined together also considering the current NBS Handbook on Indicators and Assessment).

This list should also include the definition of “bottom-up” and “place-based” indicators resulting from the co-creation process with citizens.

When defining these indicators, one could envisage the creation of a matrix for the 4 projects. For instance, such a matrix could be based on the type of solution (not only NBS but also social, digital, and cultural ones); general impacts on health; general impacts on wellbeing; place-specific impacts.

- To be updated on the work carried out on NBS Indicators and Assessment, one representative per project should participate in the existing Taskforce 2. Please contact Veronica.RUIZ@iucn.org;

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adina.dumitru@udc.es; and Laura.Wendling@vtt.fi to add the representative from your project (put your PA in Cc).

2.2 Actions developed by the IN-HABIT project

IN-HABIT has developed a context-based set of subjective and objective indicators to measure the results of the visionary and integrated solutions (VIS) on citizens' Inclusive Health and Wellbeing.

To this aim, the project partners have worked to define health and wellbeing as a common pool resource which can be analysed as a multi-dimensional asset of human life in the cities, which also involves animals, nature, and culture. The following dimensions of health and wellbeing have been considered for the purposes of assessing the impact of the IN-HABIT project:

- Social well-being, which includes social cohesion, crime/security and violence, social inclusion, equality, discrimination, spatial well-being.
- Mental health, which includes psychological well-being, positive emotions, and life satisfaction.
- Healthy lifestyles, which include health determinants, physical health status, sports practice, mobility, cultural habits, and leisure/use of free time.
- Economic well-being, which includes employment and employability, job and skills satisfaction, poverty and income, education, housing.

The sub-dimensions of health and wellbeing, as well as the related subjective indicators have been selected by means of a co-design process. The theoretical and empirical assumptions of the researchers have been integrated with the views of local inhabitants and representatives of local organizations on the expected changes on people's health and wellbeing as partly attributable to the solutions envisaged in the 4 pilot cities. The needs of people with personal characteristics related with the Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion perspective of the project have been considered by involving them in group discussions and individual interviews.

The selected indicators have been grouped in three meta-categories based on the following criteria:

1. Capacity to reveal and describe those elements of the social, institutional, and economic context of the 4 pilot cities, which may influence health and well-being and its equitable distributions among social groups (**Context Indicators**).

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2. Capacity to detect the differences among social groups and individuals based on personal characteristics which may affect health and well-being and the impact of the VIS (**GDEI indicators**).
3. Capacity to measure and isolate the changes (both expected and unexpected), which are attributable, in whole or in part, to the VIS that will be tested in the 4 cities (**Key Impact Indicators**).

Additionally, the design of the indicators has been guided by the following methodological objectives:

- **Comparability:** selected indicators should be able to measure those aspects of health and well-being which are considered by the main European and International statistics and research frameworks (OECD, Eurostat, European Commission, UNDP/SDGs, other H2020-funded projects), to ensure comparability and to fill the gaps in terms of data availability on urban development that promotes inclusive health and wellbeing in small and medium size cities.
- **Specificity:** selected indicators should be meaningful and relevant to the specific local context of the 4 pilot cities, since they refer to existing and measurable characteristics of the local population, project solutions, socio-economic and institutional context, also considering the Covid-19 pandemic. For this reason, many indicators have been borrowed from international standards and their formulation has been changed and adapted to the local context, while other new and complementary indicators have been formulated.
- **Inclusiveness and citizen science use:** the subjective indicators consider both the researchers' and the citizens' assumptions on expected changes affecting health and well-being, with specific regard to the perspective of those people who identified themselves as representatives of the groups with GED&I personal characteristics at local level.

2.3 Actions suggested by the IN-HABIT project

Based on the conclusions of the second clustering meeting, IN-HABIT may contribute:

1. To the production of the **Manifesto** with a common narrative on the subsidiarity principle applied to well-being and health. In this respect, IN-HABIT will provide operational examples of the "local dimension" of inclusive health and well-being resulting from the co-design of indicators, as well as a conceptual framework to help defining the subsidiarity principle applied to health and well-being. The project also will contribute to the co-definition of the

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term ‘locality’ in the city IN-HUBs and to the alignment of the Manifesto with the OECD approach to wellbeing at regional level.

In fact, in WP7, the IN-HABIT project has identified some collective aspects of health and well-being which are closely related to the urban dimension, since:

- They arise from the relationship between people and the built and natural environment (i.e., spatial well-being, sense of belonging).
 - They arise from the relationship between citizens and the opportunities provided by the urban fabric (i.e., institutional support and services, cultural and educational facilities).
 - They arise from the relationship among citizens who share the same urban space (i.e., trust, social capital, social relations, inclusion).
2. IN-HABIT may contribute to the production of the joint deliverable, based on a consensus list of common key impact indicators to measure the impact of the VIS to improve health and well-being at urban level and considering the current *NBS Handbook on Indicators and Assessment*.

IN-HABIT partners will participate in the different activities organised to define these indicators and will populate the mentioned matrix for each of the solutions (NBS, social, cultural, and digital).

ISIM Partner could particularly contribute to the definition of such indicators, by supporting the process of cooperation in this way:

- Defining/categorizing the key characteristics of the solutions across the SC5-14 projects.
- Defining the expected changes and indicators on health and well-being in relation to the key characteristics.

IN-HABIT City Partners will present the final indicators and test them with local citizens in IN-HUBs workshops and meetings, for them to be representative of local approaches to inclusive health and wellbeing.

Among these indicators, ISIM could also help defining:

- Those which have been designed throughout a “bottom-up” and “place-based” process.

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- The correspondence with the NBS Handbook, by highlighting similarities, overlapping and novelty.
3. In addition to this, ISIM, UREAD and UCO could also help identifying common indicators and questions to detect GDEI personal characteristics and to disaggregate primary data, accordingly.

3. GENDER, DIVERSITY, EQUITY, AND INCLUSION (GDEI)

The main outputs of this cooperation area would be:

- To appoint a GDEI Manager in each project to monitor all co-creation and co-deployment activities.
- To develop a common co-creation strategy to include and effectively engage diverse groups of citizens according to a diverse set of personal characteristics (i.e., sex, age, gender, sexual orientation, disability, ethnicity, etc.). This common set of personal characteristics will need to be identified ex-ante by the four GDEI Managers.
- Innovative technologies to monitor progress and bottlenecks in GDEI (i.e., AI to tackle unconscious bias, AI for emotion recognition, biosensors, etc.). The proposed innovative technologies could be included in the common co-creation strategy.
- To draft 2 joint deliverables: *GDEI toolkit for health and wellbeing in cities* and *Artificial Intelligence and GDEI*

3.1 Actions agreed in the Second Online Clustering Meeting

After the 2nd Online Clustering Meeting celebrated on 27th February, the representative partners of the sister projects agreed to develop the following actions:

1. **Nominate a GDEI manager + the main lead on cocreation and co-deployment activities.**

The GDEI managers and the leads on co-creation will define common modalities to engage diverse citizens remotely due to the current COVID-19 pandemic. This will allow them to address the digital divide not only in terms of rural/urban cleavage but also in terms of different abilities that citizens have when using online technologies and tools.

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The results of these co-creation activities to engage diverse citizens during the COVID-19 pandemic could also be reflected in a joint deliverable on cocreation to harvest the richness of process.

2. **A common strategy to define the set of personal characteristics** (i.e., sex, age, gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, ethnicity, etc.) to be included when engaging diverse citizens.

The work carried out in this respect could result in a joint deliverable on GDEI toolkit for health and wellbeing in cities. This toolkit could reflect similar work done by other international organisations on DEI for the labour market. See for instance [World Economic Forum \(2020\) Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion 4.0: A toolkit for leaders to accelerate social progress in the future of work](#).

Concerning age as a personal characteristic, please have a look at the new Commission Green Paper on [Ageing: Fostering solidarity and responsibility between generations](#) (27 January 2021). More information available [here](#).

3. **A joint deliverable/positioning paper on AI and GDEI** (i.e., AI to tackle unconscious bias, AI for emotion recognition, biosensors, etc.). Such a deliverable should also consider the current debate on AI and discrimination. See for instance [AINOW \(2019\) Discriminating Systems: Gender, Race and Power in AI](#).

3.2 Actions developed by the IN-HABIT project

The GDEI Manager in the IN-HABIT Project was appointed from the start of the project. Prof. Dr. Marina Della Giusta from the University of Reading (UREAD) is playing this role.

UREAD is responsible for:

- Sampling frames for surveys 1 (by UREAD) and 2 (by ISIMPACT).
- Behavioural games.
- Gendered landscapes in the 4 pilot cities.

These tasks consider personal characteristics. All of them require the use of administrative data, that is individual anonymised records of residents attainable from a variety of sources (e.g., census records, national statistical office records, social security records, health authorities' records, city registers -for example to identify same sex couples-). Only at this level of data it is possible to link demographic characteristics (such as gender, age, ethnicity, marital status, number, and ages of children...) and basic

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socioeconomic variables of interest (such as physical and mental health status, education level, tenancy type, income levels, employment status...).

Cities are also in the process to identify appropriate CONTROL areas (where INHABIT will NOT affect citizens), which should have the most possible similar sociodemographic profiles to the INTERVENTION areas (IN-HABIT selected areas).

Figure 1. Sampling proposal

What UREAD will do with the data:

- Using administrative data, they will check that they have close to random samples of citizens to take part in surveys and games (they will be recruited with different methods on the ground and online depending on the activity).
- Outcomes for these samples (intervention and control) will be then measured by surveys 1 and 2 and by behavioural games.
- Construction of gendered landscapes.

The list of GDEI indicators would provide a detailed account of the GDEI profile of the INHABIT areas. The approach to data collection would ensure that all indicators are collected by the relevant characteristics, including:

- Sex or Gender
- Ethnicity (or nation of birth)
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation

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- Religion or belief

If possible, in some cases, it would be helpful to have indicators that capture the intersectionality between more than one characteristic: gender and age, gender and ethnicity...If possible, in some cases, it will be important to have indicators not just for the city level but for the more granular geographical level, to build a profile of the neighbourhoods/areas IN-HABIT is working on.

All indicators must be at the city level and for all relevant GDEI characteristics when possible. However, not all the indicators can be collected for all the above GDEI characteristics or by the more granular geographical level.

Additionally, IN-HABIT project includes *D5.1 Stakeholder Engagement with GDEI perspective Toolkit* that will provide guidelines, methods, and tools for stakeholder engagement. D5.1 is led by TSR partner, but other partners play a key role in its development such as UREAD, ISIM, BOT and UCO. The delivery date is 30 June 2021 and researchers are already working in its elaboration.

3.3 Actions suggested by the IN-HABIT project

Based on the conclusions of the second clustering meeting, IN-HABIT may contribute by:

1. Participating in the working group and in the deliverable that will define modalities to engage diverse citizens remotely and identify good practices and main barriers especially when working with GDEI approaches. UREAD, UCO and TSR researchers will participate and share their expertise with the other participants.
2. Joint discussion on the tools included in D5.1 with sister projects to agree on the set of personal characteristics to be included when engaging diverse citizens and to align IN-HABIT proposals with those of international organisations such as the World Economic Forum or the European Commission. UREAD, UCO and TSR researchers will participate and share their expertise with the other participants.
3. Participating in the discussions and in the elaboration of a joint deliverable/ positioning paper on AI and GDEI. The expertise of WTG and UCO in AI might contribute to this task.

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4. JOINT COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The main outputs of this area of cooperation would be the following:

- A common glossary on communication and dissemination (to be consistent both for internal communication between the 4 projects and for external communication).
- The abovementioned joint deliverables.
- Joint events (at least 2/3 conferences/workshops).
- Joint publications.
- Synergies with the new projects funded under the H2020 SC1 Health, demographic change, and wellbeing.

4.1 Actions agreed in the Second Online Clustering Meeting

After the 2nd Online Clustering Meeting celebrated on 27th February, the representative partners of the sister projects agreed to develop the following actions:

1. **A common glossary** (to be consistent both for internal communication between the 4 projects and for external communication).
2. **Joint deliverables** (i.e., the ones mentioned above)
3. **A timeline for joint events** (at least 2/3 conferences/workshops). A calendar with main events for 2021 will be shared on Teams to prepare the joint events of the projects.
4. **Synergies with the cluster of projects H2020 SC5-20-2019** on Transforming historic urban areas into hubs of entrepreneurship and social and cultural integration:

[T-FACTOR](#). Coordinator: Laura Martelloni la.martelloni@gmail.com

[HUB-IN](#). Coordinator: Vera Gregório veragregorio@lisboaenova.org

[CENTRINNO](#). Coordinator: Lucia Scopelliti Lucia.Scopelliti@comune.milano.it

5. **Synergies with the new projects funded under the H2020 SC1 Health, demographic change, and wellbeing:**

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Table 1. Projects funded under the H2020 SC1 Health, demographic change, and wellbeing:

ENLIGHTEN ME 48 months	Innovative policies for improving citizens' health and wellbeing addressing indoor and outdoor lighting	Simona Tondelli simona.tondelli@unibo.it Valerio Carelli valerio.carelli@unibo.it Vera Schneider v.schneider@eurice.eu
URBANOME 48 months	Urban observatory for multi-participatory enhancement of health and wellbeing	Denis Sarigiannis denis@eng.auth.gr
RECETAS 60 months	Re-imagining environments for connection and engagement: testing actions for social prescribing in natural spaces	Jill Litt jill.litt@isglobal.org Laura Coll Planas: Laura.Coll@uab.cat Carolyn Daher: Carolyn.Daher@isglobal.org
EMOTIONAL CITIES 48 months	eMOTIONAL Cities - Mapping the cities through the senses of those who make them	Paolo Morgado paulo@campus.ul.pt Bruno Miranda bruno.a.miranda@gmail.com
HEART 48 months	Healthier cities through blue-green regenerative technologies: the heart approach	Prof. Anastasios Doulamis, adoulam@cs.ntua.gr Prof. Nikolaos Doulamis, ndoulam@cs.ntua.gr Dr. Manthos Bimpas, mbibas@esd.ece.ntua.gr
WELLBASED 48 months	Improving health, wellbeing and equality by evidenced-based urban policies for tackling energy poverty	Elena Rocher elena.rocher@lasnaves.com Maite Ferrando mferrando@kveloce.com

4.2 Actions developed by the IN-HABIT project

IN-HABIT is developing a glossary of the main terms employed by the project, as part of the initial coordination actions. The glossary is aimed at defining a shared vocabulary among the partners. It will facilitate both the internal conversation and cooperation among the partners during the implementation, and the communication of its objectives and actions externally towards different audiences. This glossary is conceived as a component of the toolkit for the engagement of stakeholders (D5.1), being an essential instrument to outreach diverse social, professional, and cultural groups through different language environments. As such, it will be also included into the *IN-HABIT Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) strategy*. As mentioned, TSR partner in collaboration with other partners are elaborating this document that will be delivered by June 2010.

The terms included in the glossary have been selected based on the terminology employed by the submitted project description, completed with relevant words that emerged in the first phases of collaboration among the partners responsible for WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8, and from consultations with

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the four cities (WP1-4). The definitions proposed in the glossary are not conceived as exhaustive and universal acceptations of multifaceted and often fuzzy plastic words widely employed in multiple context and disciplinary environments. They aim at circumscribing clear, shared, operational meanings of these terms within the specific objectives and practices promoted by this project. Additional purpose is to facilitate correct translations of the main language of the project into the four local languages, and to support simple and inclusive formulations of its key concepts also for general non-expert audiences. Moreover, the glossary will be completed by a list of bibliographic references validating the recognition process.

IN-HABIT toolkit is currently in progress. It will have a first expected delivery before the start of the training process but is supposed to be a “living document” capturing improvements and clarifications deriving from the entire implementation of the project. The glossary development is coordinated by the TSR partner with the collaboration of other partners (UCO, BOT, ISIM, UREAD, DFC). The discussion among the partners is happening through dedicated online workshops completed through individual editing happening in between. The process is being facilitated using a collaborative Trello board collecting the definitions in process and a shared Google document presenting the last updated version. During the training of local activators, appropriate translations and strategies will be also discussed for communicating the key disciplinary terminologies to generic audiences and people with protected characteristics.

4.3 Actions suggested by the IN-HABIT project

TSR partner will share methods and in-progress outcomes of IN-HABIT common glossary and participate to clustering activities aimed at the development of the joint glossary of the four H2020 sister projects. IN-HABIT partners will contribute to the common glossary.

IN-HABIT partners will participate in the joint deliverables and positioning papers that might be developed in collaboration with sister projects and other projects included in the clustering activities.

BOT partner proposes the following communication and joint actions to strengthen dissemination and outreach actions, to be discussed with the other sister projects:

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- Coordinate with other clustering projects communication WPLs to share a common strategy towards a global outreach at a European level, especially regarding topics involving EU policies and currently debatable topics (i.e., inclusion, well-being, ageing, etc).
- Coordinate with other clustering projects communication WPLs on a regular basis (joint Task Force on comprehensive communication for very operational purposes) to share common knowledge about best practices in general, institutional communication and best practices in local communication and storytelling facing common challenges, and how to overcome them (digital divide, COVID-19 impact, engagement of citizens & vulnerable groups, children and youths, inclusiveness, etc.), or to develop a common toolbox and engage multipliers (online and social media communication, coordinated) exploitation of project outcomes.
- Work together with the sister projects on a common agenda on upcoming initiatives and events to share with EASME for information and other significant authorities.
- Collating resources: e.g., educational content, media libraries, training, and educational resources pages, gathering of examples on NBS or cultural innovation, etc.
- Create comprehensive, cross-sectional content among the projects to enhance understanding of their purpose beyond the project, at a greater level: infographics, data sheets, “killer facts.”
- Underline policy relevance in communications, as well.
- Work with clustering projects on a common glossary on communication and dissemination topics to build a strong, clear identity for dissemination purposes across target groups.
- Joint activities/events, both online and offline, for amplification: share projects internal calendars; create a common calendar of events at EU level; track relevant events and initiatives and invite relevant stakeholders/speakers, starting from sister projects sharing their experiences; organize workshop meetings on common grounds (i.e., storytelling in your neighbourhood).
- Use existing connections and networks for global outreach and international cooperation to broaden impact on social media and online communities.

Initial proposal of events to take part into or to promote on shared media

Conferences and upcoming events (to be updated)

- EU GREEN WEEK – Lathi May 2021
- European Free Leaf Award to be assigned (open to towns with 20,000 to 100, 000 inhabitants with good practices of green sustainability). The 2021 European Green Leaf title was jointly awarded to Gabrovo in Bulgaria and Lappeenranta in Finland. For 2020, the European Green Leaf title was jointly awarded to Limerick in Ireland and Mechelen in Belgium.
- IWA World Water Congress – Water for smart liveable cities, May 2021

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- Estonia: Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP) Europe Conference, June 2021
- Poland: Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit, June 2021
- University of Oxford: NBS Conference, July 2021
- Poland: 3rd World Conference of the Society for Urban Ecology, July 2021
- France: IUCN World Conservation Congress, September 2021
- UN Climate Change Conference, November 2021
- Oxford: NBS Solutions in a Changing Climate, July 2022

European Capital of Culture and related events in the following cities

- 2020 (title might be extended to 2021 due to COVID-19 to give opportunity to visit) Rijeka, Galway, Parma
- 2021 Timișoara, Elefsina, Novi Sad
- 2022 Kaunas, Esch-sur-Alzette

Green Capitals

- 2021 Lathi
- 2022 Grenoble

Youth European capitals

- 2021 Kaipėda
- 2022 Tirana

Sports European capitals

- 2021 Lisbon
- 2022 The Hague

Other events

- ROCK project – RISE IMET INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE 2021 (Emerging Technologies and the Digital Transformation of Museums and Heritage Sites), Cyprus, June 2021
- Connecting Nature Summit Series – Innovation Summit, Glasgow, March 2021
- Urban Arena Berlin: Governance for Sustainable and Just Cities, Berlin, March 2021
- REWAISE: 29th Topical Meeting on Energy and Water, April 2021
- Global Water Summit 2021, May 2021

International Days

- 21/03/21 International day for the elimination of racial discrimination 2021 and International day of forests

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- 22/03/21 World Water Day
- 24/03/21 International Day for the Right to the Truth Concerning Gross Human Rights Violations and for the Dignity of Victims
- 02/04/21 World Autism Awareness Day
- 07/04/21 World Health Day
- 21/04/21 International Creativity and Innovation Day in 2021
- 22/04/21 Earth Day 2021
- 01/05/21 International Workers' Day
- 22/05/21 International Day for Biological Diversity
- 05/06/21 World Environmental Day
- 20/06/21 World Refugees Day
- 22/06/21 World Rainforest Day
- 26/06/21 UN International Day in Support of Victims of Torture
- 03/07/21 The International Plastic Bag Free Day
- 23/09/21 International Day of Sign Languages
- 04/10/21 World Habitat Day – World Animal Day
- 17/10/21 International Day for the Eradication of poverty
- 31/10/21 World Cities Day

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